

EDAP+ TN on Quality Assessment of SPIRE L2 GNSS-R Soil Moisture

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AMENDMENT RECORD SHEET

The Amendment Record Sheet below records the history and issue status of this document.

ISSUE	DATE	REASON
0.1	31/07/2023	First Draft
1.0	22/02/2024	Final version approved by SPIRE Inc.

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

SPIRE Global is a data and Analytics Company that designs, builds, tests, operates and collects data from its satellite constellation composed of Lemur-2 satellites. Each of these satellites carry two payloads: STRATOS GPS radio occultation meteorology payload and SENSE AIS payload for ship tracking. STRATOS is the SPIRE GNSS receiver for remote sensing & precision orbit determination; a modified version of this instrument is used for passive bistatic radar (GNSS-R) applications. This technique studies the reflection of radio signals by the ground to measure several geophysical quantities. The original signal is generally emitted by another satellite, different from the receiver; STRATOS can collect the GPS signals used for geo-localization to perform opportunity measurements. The current Spire GNSS-R constellation consists of two Batch-1 satellites in a 35 degrees inclination orbit, and two Batch-2 satellites in sun-synchronous polar orbits. The Batch-2 satellites are undergoing calibration and validation activities, and so the preview L2A Land dataset is limited to the Batch-1 satellites. The Batch-1 data coverage is in the range between +/- 39 degrees latitude.

In this work we examined the SPIRE Soil Moisture Preview Product, obtained using GNSS-R technique; SPIRE collects soil moisture value from the first 5 cm of the surface. One advantage of using this technique is penetration through vegetation, where optical sensors and C-band radars have limited functionality.

SPIRE data are generally well documented, with the description of all the variables presents in the files and the presence of numerous metadata even if some information should be explained more clearly. L1 documentation deeply characterizes the sensor, the calibration, and the geometrical aspects of the measurements; the delivered L2 Product Manual describes the retrieval algorithm and some examples of characterization of the product with respect to CYGNSS and SMAP, two datasets used in the calibration process. Soil moisture uncertainty is not present.

Soil moisture Product has been intercompared with three different satellites mission: CYGNSS, SMAP and SMOS. The intercomparison region chosen is the south-east Australia, with about 30 days of data between June and July 2021. CYGNSS dataset has been chosen for the use of their historical data in the calibration processes over the south-east Australia; CYGNSS performs GNSS-R measurements, and its retrieval also inspired the algorithm employed by SPIRE. SMAP and SMOS can be considered the state-of-the-art missions in the soil moisture measurements; they employ different measurement techniques and can be considered independent datasets.

Spatial co-location threshold chosen for the intercomparison is 15 km, chosen considering the spatial resolution of the references. SPIRE passages over the intercomparison region are mainly in the morning, while SMOS and SMAP measurements are at dawn and dusk, and CYGNSS measurements are distributed every 6 hours. Several intercomparison studies have been carried on using different temporal thresholds: in particular, we present in the study the results obtained using 8 and 3 hours temporal windows. A dependence of the results from the temporal threshold has been identified: the 8 hours threshold was chosen due to the large number of points provided, covering a large portion of the intercomparison region, but we decided also to present briefly the 3 hours scatterplot to monitor the improvement of intercomparison reducing the time distance.

We found a correlation coefficient of about 0.6 for the three references with a similar bias structure: positive for values of soil moisture up to ~0.3-0.4 and negative above. The measurement distributions are similar for small values of soil moisture, while tend to move away for higher values. Spatially, the difference trends are more evident in the region at the centre of the intercomparison area and in some pixels on the coast.

Decreasing the temporal threshold improve the quality of the intercomparison for SMOS (0.77 of correlation coefficient for three hours). Some results suggest an improvement also

in for the other two references, but the low number of coincidences does not allow to consider them statistically significant.

1.1 References

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

- RD-1. EDAP Best Practice Guidelines, EDAP.REP.001, v2.1, 31st October 2021.
- RD-2. Earth Observation Mission Quality Assessment Framework ...
- RD-3. SPIRE GNSS-R Level 2A Land Product Manual, v1.3, 5th October 2022.
- RD-4. SPIRE Near-Nadir GNSS-R Level 1 Product Manual, v1.2, 1st May 2022.
- RD-5. CYGNSS Handbook, v1.0, 1st April 2016.
- RD-6. UCAR/CU CYGNSS Soil Moisture Product User Guide, 9th May 2019.
- RD-7. SMAP L3 Radiometer Global Daily 36 km EASE-Grid Soil Moisture User Guide, v8.
- RD-8. Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) Level 2 Passive Soil Moisture Product Specification Document, 13th May 2019.
- RD-9. Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document Level 2 & 3 Soil Moisture (Passive) Data Products, 31st August 2020.
- RD-10. SMOS Level 2 and Auxiliary Data Products Specification, v8/6, 31st January 2020.
- RD-11. SMOS Level 2 Soil Moisture Product ATBD, v4.0, 9th September 2019.
- RD-12. Agam, Nurit, and P. R. Berliner. "Diurnal water content changes in the bare soil of a coastal desert." *Journal of Hydrometeorology* 5.5 (2004): 922-933.

1.2 Glossary

ATBD: Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document

CYGNSS: CYclone Global Navigation Satellite System

GNSS: Global Navigation Satellite Systems

GNSS-R: Global Navigation Satellite Systems Reflectometry

SMAP: Soil Moisture Active Passive

SMOS: Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity

sm: soil moisture

1.3 Cal/Val Maturity Matrices Land

Data Provider Documentation Review			Validation Summary	Key
Product Information	Metrology	Product Generation		
Product Details	Measurement Validation Method	Not Assessed		
Availability & Accessibility	Measurement Validation Results Compliance	Not Assessable		
Product Format, Flags & Metadata	Geometric Validation Method	Basic		
User Documentation	Geometric Validation Results Compliance	Good		
	Ancillary Data			Excellent

Figure 1.3.1: Summary Matrix Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

1.3.1 Soil moisture validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

SPIRE soil moisture detailed validation				Key
Measurement		Geometric		
SPIRE vs CYGNSS Method	SPIRE vs CYGNSS Results Compliance	SPIRE vs CYGNSS Method	SPIRE vs CYGNSS Results Compliance	Not Assessed
SPIRE vs SMAP Method	SPIRE vs SMAP Results Compliance	SPIRE vs ASCAT Method	SPIRE vs ASCAT Results Compliance	Not Assessable
SPIRE vs SMOS Method	SPIRE vs SMOS Results Compliance	SPIRE vs TAO Method	SPIRE vs TAO Results Compliance	Basic
				Good
				Excellent
				Ideal
				🔒 Not Public

Figure 1.3.2: Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

2. DATA PROVIDER DOCUMENTATION REVIEW

2.1 Product Information

In the sample file are presents variables not described in the L2 user manual. These variables are, however, described in metadata.

Product Details	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Some information misses or is not explicitly reported in the provided documentation.
Product Name	Spire GNSS-R L2A Land Soil Moisture
Sensor Name	STRATOS (GNSS-R) The satellite id number which makes the measurement is present in the metadata "rx_id". Transmitter name is present in the file name.
Sensor Type	GNSS-R
Mission Type	Constellation
Mission Orbit	The current Spire GNSS-R constellation consists of two Batch-1 satellites in a 35 deg inclination orbit, and two Batch-2 satellites in sun-synchronous polar orbits. The Batch-2 satellites are undergoing calibration and validation activities, and so the preview L2A Land dataset is limited to the Batch-1 satellites. The Batch-1 data coverage is in the range between +/- 39 degrees latitude.
Product Version Number	V3.07
Product ID	Not clearly reported
Processing level of product	Level 2a
Measured Quantity Name	Soil moisture
Measured Quantity Units	m ³ m ⁻³ , dimensionless
Stated Measurement Quality	Not a direct quality grade assigned to the measurement.
Spatial Resolution	Information is not present in the metadata. Information not clearly present in RD-3, the document just refers to a 3.5 x 0.5 km along, across track as resolution for the coherent reflection measurements, but smooth processes applied on data should reduce the resolution.
Spatial Coverage	Global coverage, land.
Temporal Resolution	Revisit time not clearly presents in the metadata. Information not clearly present in RD-3
Temporal Coverage	Information on starting point for availability of the product not clearly reported in the documentation.
Point of Contact	Not present in the metadata. Information not clearly present in RD-3
Product locator (DOI/URL)	Not present in the metadata. Information not clearly present in RD-3

Conditions for access and use	Commercial Data, conditions defined by contract
Limitations on public access	Not present in the metadata. Information not clearly present in RD-3
Product Abstract	<p>GNSS-R measurements of soil moisture over land, calculated using the coherent reflectivity measurement.</p> <p>L-band GNSS-R reflectivity measurements over land vary depending on soil water content, surface roughness, and vegetation. For a given geographic location, the surface roughness can be viewed as almost constant. Seasonal changes in vegetation can still affect reflection but on a much longer time scale than changes in soil moisture. Short-term fluctuations in reflectivity (dB scale) are roughly linearly related to changes in soil moisture. A relative measure of reflectivity that corresponds to variations in soil moisture levels can be calculated by scaling the normalized reflectivity between the lowest and highest reflectivity measurements (dry and wet references in each location) that correspond in each case to the vegetation wilting point and soil saturation. The absolute soil moisture values in volumetric units can be calculated using the relative soil moisture product and high-resolution soil porosity maps (if available). Alternatively, the relative soil moisture measurements can be calibrated using concurrent historical soil moisture observations (in-situ or reliable satellite-based soil moisture). Spire uses historical soil moisture data from SMAP to extract calibration parameters necessary to generate the Spire Calibrated Surface Soil Moisture (CSSM) in a volumetric unit.</p>

Availability & Accessibility		
Grade: Good		
Justification	The proposed grade is good: products are compliant to some FAIR principles, but no Data Management Plan is provided, and no data catalogue published. This score could be increased providing them.	
Compliant with FAIR principles	<i>Partially compliant</i>	
	To be Findable:	
	F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	Yes, the file name is generated univocally
	F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)	yes
	F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes	No
	F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	No
	To be Accessible:	
A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol	No	

	A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	No
	A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary	No
	A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	No
	To be Interoperable:	
	I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	Yes
	I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	Yes
	I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	Yes, the file L1B that generates the data
	To be Reusable:	
	R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	Partially, some important information still lacks. In particular I suggest adding spatial and temporal resolution and coverage, see the previous paragraph.
	R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	Yes, but not explicitly reported in the file itself
	R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	Yes
	R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	Yes
Data Management Plan	<i>Not available to the users.</i>	
Availability Status	<i>There is no product catalogue publicly available online. Data availability defined by contract.</i>	

Product Format	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<i>It does not appear that data provider follows a standard convention for metadata. However, they are enough self-explaining. We propose a good grade.</i>
Product File Format	<i>netCDF4</i>
Metadata Conventions	<i>Metadata not clearly follows a specific convention</i>
Analysis Ready Data?	<i>No</i>

User Documentation		
Grade: Good		
Justification	The user provides a PUG that explains how the product is derived and the retrieval algorithm, referring also to scientific literature for further details.	
<i>Document</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>QA4ECV Compliant</i>
Product User Guide	Spire GNSS-R Preview Level 2A Land Product Manual	No
ATBD	Spire GNSS-R Preview Level 2A Land Product Manual	No

2.2 Metrology

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	The calibration chain and equations are described in RD-4 with an example of calibration relative power between front-end. In ground testing, The calibration system was shown to meet the requirement of power ratio measurement calibration better than +/- 0.25 dB. Additionally, all the key components of the instrumentation are described (e.g., antenna gains).
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Spire Near-Nadir GNSS-R Level 1 Product Manual</i>

Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Antenna gains and sensibilities with respect to signal directions are documented in RD-4 and considered fit for purpose.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Spire Near-Nadir GNSS-R Level 1 Product Manual</i>

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Traceability chain briefly described in L1 User Manual; uncertainty diagram is not present in the provided documentation
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Spire Near-Nadir GNSS-R Level 1 Product Manual</i>

Uncertainty Characterisation	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	Uncertainty not provided.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>GNSS-R Preview Level 2A Land Product Manual</i>

Ancillary Data	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>Spire uses historical SMAP data to extract calibration parameters needed for generating the Spire Calibrated Surface Soil Moisture (CSSM) in volumetric units.</p> <p>CYGNSS historical data mean of reflectivity are used in the process of Reflectivity Noise Reduction.</p> <p>The mean of CYGNSS reflectivity is used also to identify areas of low reflection quality because of complex topography or densely vegetated areas.</p> <p>ESA CCI 300 m permanent water bodies map is used for setting the permanent water bodies flag.</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>GNSS-R Preview Level 2A Land Product Manual</i>

2.3 Product Generation

Calibration Algorithm	
Grade: Good	
Justification	The signal injection approach couples a calibration signal into each of the front ends. This approach is commonly used for the calibration of phased array antennas and allows measurement of phase as well as amplitude. Data from land and ocean are processed with different chains. Signal and calibration quantities reported in L1 files.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Spire Near-Nadir GNSS-R Level 1 Product Manual</i>

Geometric Processing	
Grade: Good	
Justification	The Geometric Processing is described in detail in the RD-4. Geometric information is detailly documented in the L1 files.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Spire Near-Nadir GNSS-R Level 1 Product Manual</i>

Retrieval Algorithm	
Grade: Good	
Justification	The retrieval process is documented in [RD-3], with references to the literature and CYGNSS algorithm. Example of application of retrieval algorithm are shown with a qualitative comparison with SMAP and CYGNSS data. A sensitivity study, however, should be added to the user manual to fully achieve the good grade. Giving the 'on-development' nature of this product, we suggest providing a deeper insight on the algorithm performances on the user manual.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>GNSS-R Preview Level 2A Land Product Manual</i>

Mission-Specific Processing	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	<i>No Additional Processing documented for the product.</i>
Reference	<i>GNSS-R Preview Level 2A Land Product Manual</i>

3. DETAILED VALIDATION – MEASUREMENT

3.1 Introduction

GNSS Reflectometry (GNSS-R) involves making measurements of the reflections from the Earth of navigation signals from the Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS). SPIRE employs GNSS Bistatic Radar (gbr) observations of the land to retrieve surface soil moisture. The soil moisture values are derived from the measured intensity of the reflected signal calibrated using model parameters derived from long-term time series of NASA's Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) or Cyclone Global Navigation Satellite System (CYGNSS) measurements. In this chapter we propose a brief intercomparison exercise from soil moisture measurements of SPIRE with those retrieved by other missions.

We received SPIRE soil moisture data for the periods 1st-22nd June, 2021 and 1st-7th July 2021 over the south west of Australia, between about [-26, -38] deg of latitude and [139, 155] deg of longitude (see Figure 3.1.1). The region is characterized by humid coasts, rich of vegetation with coastal reliefs and an internal desartic area.

Figure 3.1.1: satellite view of the intercomparison region.

The provided data have been measured by the single FM109 satellite (receiver satellite information present on metadata) and data used for calibration comes from historical soil moisture measurements of CYGNSS, version 6.02 (even this information is present on metadata). SPIRE does not provide an uncertainty value for soil moisture; for this reason, during the intercomparison, if more than one SPIRE measurement can be co-located with a reference measurement, the standard deviation will be used as an estimate of the uncertainty.

The first references selected for the intercomparison are CYGNSS and SMAP: CYGNSS inspired SPIRE retrieval while SMAP historical data are usually employed in the calibration algorithm ([RD-3]) even if in this case the CYGNSS dataset has been used for this purpose (see above); these two references cannot be considered fully independent from SPIRE measurements, however the intercomparison results will provide an insight of SPIRE capability with respect of the datasets that directly inspired the retrieval rationale. The third satellite reference chosen is SMOS.

CYGNSS is a NASA Earth Venture mission, managed by the Earth System Science Pathfinder Program. The mission consists of a constellation of eight small satellites flying in 510 km circular orbits at a common inclination of 35, 302 and 260 deg. CYGNSS, as SPIRE, employs the GNSS-R technique for the measurement. For intercomparison, we selected the Level 3 Soil Moisture Product, that provides volumetric water content estimates for soils between 0-5 cm depth at a 6-hour discretization for most of the subtropics. The soil moisture algorithm uses collocated soil moisture retrievals from SMAP to calibrate CYGNSS observations from the same day. For a given location, a linear relationship between the SMAP soil moisture and CYGNSS reflectivity is determined and used to transform the CYGNSS observations into soil moisture. CYGNSS measurements have a spatial minimum resolution of $[7 \times 0.5]$ km, along/across track; as for SPIRE this is just a nominal resolution, for the roughness of the terrain can produce incoherent scattering that increase the area from which the reflected signal is received. Additionally, CYGNSS is calibrated using SMAP data, that has a resolution up to 40 km; for this reason CYGNSS, in the Level3 product used in the intercomparison, measurements resolution have been degraded to the final grid of $[36 \times 36]$ km. CYGNSS values are the average of all observations for a particular grid cell in 6-hour intervals, which are currently midnight – 6am, 6am – noon, noon – 6pm, and 6pm – midnight (utc). In the following study we used as measurement time, the central time of each interval (3am, 9am, 3pm and 9pm utc). Detailed information on CYGNSS and its soil moisture retrieval can be found on [RD-5] and [RD-6].

Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) is a NASA environmental monitoring satellite that measures soil moisture across the planet with near-global revisit coverage in 2–3 days. The satellite flies at about 681 km of altitude with a sun-synchronous orbit of 98.12 deg inclination. SMAP measures the surface brightness temperature to obtain the soil moisture of the first 5 cm of the ground with a native resolution of about 36 km. For this study we used SMAP L3 soil moisture data [RD-8], also containing information about soil roughness and vegetation opacity, that will be used for a qualitative characterization of the analysed terrain. SMAP data are considered to be one of the most accurate existing soil moisture product; for this study we analyzed the Dual Channel Algorithm data, as suggested by [RD-7].

The Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity (SMOS) mission, launched on 2 November 2009, is one of the European Space Agency's Earth Explorer missions. It has an orbit altitude of about 758 km with an inclination of 98.42 deg. It boards MIRAS, Microwave Imaging Radiometer using Aperture Synthesis instrument, a passive microwave 2-D interferometric radiometer (L-Band, 1.4 GHz, 21 cm). MIRAS measures microwave emissions from Earth's surface to map levels of soil moisture, sea surface salinity, sea ice thickness and others geophysical variable such as wind speed over ocean and freeze / thaw soil state. The collection used in the intercomparison is SMOS L1 and L2 Science Data; the dataset has a spatial resolution of about 43 km with a measurement accuracy generally better than 0.04 ([RD-10], and [RD-11]).

3.2 Pre-analysis considerations

All measurements used in the following study have been screened according to the quality flags and criteria reported in their respective documentation. SPIRE measurements have been screened according to the variable's *quality_flag* and *sm_quality_flag*. SMAP data have been screened using the variable *retrieval_qual_flag*, while SMOS data have been screened according to the *Confidence_Flags* variable (in particular we discarded the measurement which are marked as outside of acceptable range for several retrieval parameters, see [RD-10]). CYGNSS dataset is an L3 screened product. The total number of SPIRE data was 67822, after the screening they reduced to 33506.

Figure 3.2.1, Figure 3.2.2 and Figure 3.2.3 show the characteristics of terrain as measured by SMAP, during the intercomparison period. The three parameters analysed are respectively the terrain roughness, the vegetation opacity, and the water content in the

vegetation. The maps have been obtained averaging together SMAP measurements within a grid of 1 deg of latitude and longitude (variables *roughness*, *vegetation_opacity*, *vegetation_water_content*). High values of one of these three parameters will result in an increase in the difficulties of the measurement, due to the introduction of an incoherent scattering component in the retrieval. The vegetation is concentrated along the coast, while in the inland the desert biome is predominant. The reliefs, associated to a larger roughness value of measurements are present along the south-west coast and in the north-east, extending into the desert.

Figure 3.2.1: SMAP roughness coefficient.

Figure 3.2.2: SMAP vegetation opacity.

The standard deviation of the three maps calculated in the binning process of the map is reported in Figure 3.2.4, Figure 3.2.5 and Figure 3.2.6. These maps give a measurement of the internal variability of the single pixels. The minimum and maximum values of the colour scale are the same used for the previous map. The low level of the standard deviation measured reveal a small variability inside a single pixel; in the desert the ratio between standard deviation and values of the vegetation opacity and water content can be

even higher than 60% but this is due to the very low levels of these parameters in this biome.

Figure 3.2.3: SMAP vegetation water content.

Figure 3.2.4: SMAP roughness coefficient standard deviation.

Figure 3.2.5: SMAP vegetation opacity standard deviation.

N

Figure 3.2.6: SMAP vegetation water content standard deviation.

In this study we will make use of the difference uncertainty, calculated as the squared sum of the two datasets uncertainty. We will also define difference-uncertainty ratio, or more simply ratio, the ratio between the differences and their combined uncertainty and the concept of **significant difference**, defined as two measurements whose difference/uncertainty ratio will be greater than 1 (difference larger than uncertainty).

SMAP reference does not provide an uncertainty value for each observation; the variables *soil_moisture_error* of the files actually contains fill values, as stated by [RD-8]. For this reason, we examined the SMAP ATBD [RD-9] searching a value to use for SMAP uncertainties. Document also reports a graph on which the soil moisture retrieval error is shown as function of the vegetation water content (page 45). For vegetation water content from 0 to 4 kg/m², soil moisture errors are within about 0.04. Considering that the larger part of the terrain of the intercomparison region is dominated by desert and that it reaches about 4 kg/m² just in few pixels near the coast, we decided to employ the average uncertainty value suggested for the Dual Channel Algorithm of 0.0323. The average SMAP

uncertainty value corresponds on the analysed graph in the [RD-9] to the uncertainty for a vegetation water content of about 2.67 kg/m²; the number of pixels with vegetation water content above this value is 16 for a total of 170 pixels composing the map. Assigning this uncertainty, we overestimate the uncertainty of SMAP measurements in the desert and introduce an underestimation just on 9.4% pixels near the coasts.

3.3 Co-location methods

The next step to the intercomparison exercise is to find the spatial and temporal co-located measurements from the datasets. The spatial and temporal threshold for coupling measurements will be assigned considering the spatial and temporal synoptic scale characterizing the soil moisture and trying to minimize the spatial and temporal distance and maximize the number of co-located observations. If more of one observation of one or both instruments are present in a certain colocation area respecting the temporal selection criteria, they are averaged together and considered as a unique measurement with uncertainty equal to the averaged uncertainty. This method avoids redundancy in the formation of the couples. Also, as explained above, due to the fact that SPIRE measurements do not have an uncertainty value, if more than one observation can be co-located with a reference measurement, the standard deviation of the observations will be used as uncertainty.

Soil moisture can greatly change with the surface condition, even within few kilometres and near river and coast, so the maximum horizontal distance should be as short as possible. Considering, however, the horizontal resolution of the reference products (of the order of square with more than 30 km side for CYGNSS and SMAP and 43 km for SMOS), we selected 0.14 deg as maximum latitude and 0.16 deg as maximum longitude distance (about 15 km) for CYGNSS and SMAP. Also, the soil moisture can be affected by diurnal cycle in several environment, such as coastal deserts, as reported in [RD-12]. The intercomparison period is during austral winter. Figure 3.3.1 reports the histogram of the overpass time of SPIRE, CYGNSS and SMAP in UTC and solar time (hour of Sydney). SPIRE peaks occur in the morning, while SMAP and SMOS passages are in correspondence of dawn and dusk. CYGNSS data are equally spaced during the 24 hours (CYGNSS measurements are averaged on 6 hours).

Figure 3.3.1: overpass time histogram (hours in UTC).

We explored different temporal thresholds in the preparation of the study. The results of these tests are reported in Table 1 in which the correlation coefficient, the number of points

and the mean and standard deviation of the difference can be found. The increase in the SMOS correlation coefficient and the decreasing the temporal threshold could suggest the importance of the temporal scale in soil moisture variations; however, similar test has been done with the other two satellites data, but the decrease of the temporal threshold does not lead to significative changes. We found some exceptions with 1 hour test for CYGNSS and 3 hours test for SMAP, but the number of couples found has been considered too low, covering just a small portion of the intercomparison area and a limited number of days. Generally, also, the different tests belonging to the same satellites share similar features (shape of the measurement distribution, mean bias as function of the reference measurements, etc.).

The larger part of SPIRE measurements is collected during day, while both SMAP and SMOS measurements are collected during night or dawn/dusk; reducing the temporal threshold could mitigate this discrepancy in the measurement condition, at the coast of a rapid decrease in the number of couples, especially for SMAP. In order to maximize the number of couples we decided to present the results obtained with a temporal threshold of 8 hours; reducing the threshold does not lead to better correlation coefficient for CYGNSS and SMAP and in this way also we could couple the SPIRE morning measurements with both dawn and dusk SMAP passage; both these passages collect measurements in similar illumination conditions. The same threshold will be also employed for SMOS and CYGNSS, in order to facilitate the comparison between results. In the intercomparison are also presented the scatterplot and the measurement histogram referring the 3 hours threshold, to underline the differences in the statistical results related to the variation of the time distance.

Table 1: correlation coefficient vs spatial-temporal thresholds

Thresholds	SMOS			SMAP			CYGNSS		
	Corr	num	Bias	Corr	num	Bias	Corr	Num	Bias
8 hours, 15 km	0.64	3126	0.037 ± 0.095	0.58	780	0.032 ± 0.096	0.61	988	0.078 ± 0.100
8 hours, 7.5 km	0.64	2434	0.034 ± 0.096	0.61	569	0.030 ± 0.097	0.60	890	0.080 ± 0.098
6 hours, 15 km	0.69	2284	0.041 ± 0.087	0.59	492	0.035 ± 0.096	0.62	917	0.078 ± 0.100
4 hours, 15 km	0.70	1722	0.041 ± 0.083	0.58	273	0.035 ± 0.101	0.61	782	0.082 ± 0.101
3 hours, 15 km	0.77	880	0.038 ± 0.076	0.80	69	0.047 ± 0.085	0.61	449	0.079 ± 0.101
2 hours, 15 km	0.85	244	0.042 ± 0.064	0.45	15	0.038 ± 0.089	0.63	242	0.083 ± 0.099

1 hours, 15 km							0.74	61	0.079 ± 0.085
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Figure 3.3.2: number of couples at day vs time.

Figure 3.3.2 shows the number of co-located couples found on each day of the intercomparison period on the entire intercomparison region. SPIRE - CYGNSS couples are represented by blue and red dots, SPIRE - SMAP couples are represented by purple and red stars, SPIRE - SMOS couples are represented by green and red diamonds; red markers highlight the days with no couples. The total number of couples formed according to the described criteria is 988 for CYGNSS and 780 for SMAP, and 3126 for SMOS their location is shown in Figure 3.3.3, Figure 3.3.4 and Figure 3.3.5.

Figure 3.3.3: SPIRE and CYGNSS co-located soil moisture measurements.

Figure 3.3.4: SPIRE and SMAP co-located soil moisture measurements.

Figure 3.3.5: SPIRE and SMOS co-located soil moisture measurements.

Hereinafter the results presented in the study (scatterplot, qq-plot, temporal and spatial analysis) will employ just co-located measurements.

3.4 SPIRE vs CYGNSS results

In this paragraph the results of SPIRE and CYGNSS soil moisture intercomparison will be discussed.

3.4.1 Spatial and temporal analysis

The following plots show a spatial and temporal analysis of SPIRE results, compared to CYGNSS measurements. Figure 3.4.1 shows the spatial distribution of the number of

couples. The intercomparison region has been divided into sectors of 1 deg in latitude and longitude.

Figure 3.4.1: SPIRE-CYGNSS spatial distribution of the number of couples.

Figure 3.4.2 shows the daily averages of the SPIRE (blue) and CYGNSS (orange) results. Each dot represents the average value of the co-located measurements collected during a certain day on the entire intercomparison region. The shaded area represents the daily average of the uncertainty (averaged on the entire intercomparison region). SPIRE measurements present a positive bias with respect to CYGNSS, even if a correlation is visible between the timeseries; the larger part of the time-series differences is significant.

Figure 3.4.3 shows the absolute and relative difference between the timeseries. The zero-difference line is marked in orange and the shaded area represent the difference uncertainty, calculated as squared sum of the shaded areas of the time-series plot.

Figure 3.4.2: daily averages of SPIRE and CYGNSS measurements (spatially averaged on the entire intercomparison region).

Figure 3.4.3: temporal differences between SPIRE and CYGNSS datasets (averaged spatially).

Figure 3.4.4 and Figure 3.4.5 show the maps of SPIRE and CYGNSS co-located measurements. These graphs have been built averaging together all co-located measurements in a certain region (1 deg latitude and 1 deg longitude) collected during the entire intercomparison period. Both satellites observe an increase in the soil moisture from the inland to the coastal area. However, SPIRE map tends to measure higher values of soil moisture in the central region of the intercomparison area, extending from south-west to north-east, as can be seen in Figure 3.4.6 and Figure 3.4.7. This region can be identified as desert from the satellite map in Figure 3.1.1, Figure 3.2.2 and Figure 3.2.3 and not present particular roughness (see Figure 3.2.1). Some spatial differences statistical parameters are reported in Table 2.

Figure 3.4.4: SPIRE map.

Figure 3.4.5: CYGNSS map.

Table 2: spatial differences statistics

	mean	Standard deviation	min	max
Delta	0.076	0.062	-0.129	0.228

Figure 3.4.6: SPIRE vs CYGNSS difference map.

Figure 3.4.7: SPIRE vs CYGNSS relative difference map.

In order to evaluate the uncertainty of the two datasets (remember that SPIRE uncertainty is estimated just using the standard deviation if more than one co-located measurement is present), Figure 3.4.8 and Figure 3.4.9 show the uncertainty maps.

Figure 3.4.8: SPIRE uncertainty map.

Figure 3.4.9: CYGNSS uncertainty map.

SPIRE uncertainty/standard deviation is higher in the central region, revealing a larger variability characterizing those pixels; the relative uncertainty reported in Figure 3.4.10 and Figure 3.4.11, is within 35% even in the desert, where the soil moisture values are quite low, with the maximum in correspondence of the north/west region characterized by lowest values of soil moisture. CYGNSS uncertainty tends to increase with larger value of soil moisture near the coast even if a relative minimum can be seen in the east coast.

Figure 3.4.10: SPIRE relative uncertainty map.

Figure 3.4.11: CYGNSS relative uncertainty map.

Figure 3.4.12 reports the ratio between the map differences and the difference uncertainty. This plot is useful to individuate regions in which the difference is significant. The larger part of the map present significant differences, in particular in the central region with some very high ratio pixels present also near the coasts.

Figure 3.4.12: ratio between SPIRE vs CYGNSS difference and difference uncertainty.

3.4.2 Statistical analysis

Figure 3.4.13 shows the scatter plot between CYGNSS (x axis) and SPIRE (y axis) measurements. The fit results and bias analysis of the two datasets is reported in Table 3. The mean bias value is higher than the mean CYGNSS uncertainty, suggesting the larger part of the differences will be significant.

Table 3: SPIRE vs CYGNSS statistics

	SPIRE - CYGNSS
Number of couples	988
Fit slope	0.78
Fit intercept	0.11
Correlation Coefficient	0.61
Bias Mean value	0.078
Bias Standard deviation	0.100
Mean uncertainty	0.049

Figure 3.4.13: SPIRE vs CYGNSS scatterplot (8 hours).

In order to appreciate the variations in the statistical results due to the reduction of the temporal threshold, Figure 3.4.16 presents the scatterplot obtained for 3 hours temporal threshold; for CYGNSS the reduction of the temporal threshold does not introduce significant improvements.

Figure 3.4.14: SPIRE vs CYGNSS scatterplot (3 hours).

Figure 3.4.15 shows the measurements distribution of SPIRE and CYGNSS co-located couples in terms of relative occurrences of a certain measurement result (bin width equal to 0.04). Both distributions reveal a peak in the 0.1 bin, but SPIRE has a larger occurrence in the [0.22-0.5] region of the measurement spectrum. Similar features can be seen in Figure 3.4.16, presenting the histogram obtained using 3 hours temporal threshold.

Figure 3.4.15: SPIRE and CYGNSS co-located measurements histogram (8 hours).

Figure 3.4.16: SPIRE and CYGNSS co-located measurements histogram (3 hours).

Figure 3.4.17: SPIRE V1 vs CYGNSS qq-plots; (left) comparison of the two datasets with the gaussian theoretical distribution, (right) comparison of SPIRE and CYGNSS data distribution.

Figure 3.4.17 reports the result of the quantile-quantile plot, a statistical instrument that can be employed to visually investigate the statistical distribution of the two datasets. In the left panel each dataset (blue for SPIRE, orange for CYGNSS) has been compared with the gaussian distribution that best fits its measurements, represented by the blue and yellow lines for SPIRE and CYGNSS datasets respectively. In the y-axis the values of measurements are represented, while the x-axis represents the values of a gaussian distribution expressed in terms of number of standard deviations. The two datasets have a similar distribution characterizing low values of soil moisture, diverging in the central part of the measurement spectrum.

The second panel is an inter-comparison of the distribution of the two datasets. The distribution of the quantiles of the two instruments shows again that the two datasets have a similar statistical distribution for the lower part of the measurement spectrum, until 0.1.

The central part of the measured spectrum is characterized by a linear behaviour (see also the panel one distributions), maybe suggesting some discrepancy in the calibration processes.

Figure 3.4.18: SPIRE-CYGNSS differences vs CYGNSS measurements.

Figure 3.4.19: number of couples per bin (bin width 0.04).

Figure 3.4.18 shows the differences between SPIRE and CYGNSS plotted against CYGNSS soil moisture (orange dots) and the mean and standard deviation of this difference. These last two quantities have been calculated dividing the measurements value in bins of 0.04 of. This graph shows a positive bias with a maximum in the [0.2-0.24] bin, decreasing for higher soil moisture results. Average values above 0.4 should be considered carefully due to the lower number of points for those bins (see Figure 3.4.19).

Figure 3.4.20: SPIRE-CYGNSS difference histogram

Figure 3.4.21: Histogram of ratio between difference and difference uncertainty. The coloured area is reported in the legend.

Figure 3.4.20 shows the histogram of the differences between SPIRE and CYGNSS and the results of a gaussian fit (dashed lines). The histogram bins width is again 0.04 and the gauss fit mean and standard deviation are reported in figure. The discrepancy between these numbers and the values shown in Table 3 is due to the non-perfect gaussian distribution of the differences, particularly evident in the right tail.

Figure 3.4.21 displays the histograms of the values of the ratio between SPIRE-CYGNSS differences and difference uncertainty. Histograms has been built using 1 width bins. Only 39.7% of the couples present differences within their combined uncertainty (green area), while the larger part present significant positive differences (red and yellow areas, 53.5%); cyan and purple areas referring to significant negative differences represent just less than 5% of the total.

Figure 3.4.22 shows the ratio between differences and combined uncertainties ($r = \Delta/\sigma$) as function of the CYGNSS measurement values (blue dots). The bins in this analysis are the same of those used for Figure 3.4.18. The green curve represents the average of the ratios calculated within a certain measurement bin (bins widths equal to 0.04), with the standard deviation shown by the green area. The frequency of ratios with absolute value larger than 1 (e.g., significant differences, larger than the combined uncertainty) per bin is displayed by the orange histogram in Figure 3.4.23. These plots reveal as the larger part of SPIRE measurement present significant differences as an effect of the presence of the bias between the datasets.

Figure 3.4.22: Study of the ratio between differences and uncertainties as function of CYGNSS measurements.

Figure 3.4.23: Significant differences occurrence per CYGNSS measurement bin (bin width 0.04).

3.5 SPIRE vs SMAP results

In this paragraph the results of SPIRE and SMAP soil moisture intercomparison will be discussed.

3.5.1 Spatial and temporal analysis

The following plots show a spatial and temporal analysis of SPIRE results, compared to SMAP measurements. Figure 3.5.1 shows the spatial distribution of the number of couples. The intercomparison region has been divided into sectors of 1 deg in latitude and longitude.

Figure 3.5.1: SPIRE-SMAP spatial distribution of the number of couples.

Figure 3.5.2: daily averages of SPIRE and SMAP measurements (spatially averaged on the entire intercomparison region).

Figure 3.5.2 shows the daily averages of the SPIRE (blue) SMAP (purple) results. Each dot represents the average value of the co-located measurements collected during a certain day on the entire intercomparison region. The shaded area represents the daily

average of the uncertainty (averaged on the entire intercomparison region). The two timeseries appear to be correlated; bias is averaged less pronounced with respect to CYGNSS.

Figure 3.5.3 shows the absolute and relative difference between the timeseries. The zero-difference line is marked in orange and the shaded area represent the difference uncertainty, calculated as squared sum of the shaded areas of the time-series plot. The larger part of the analysed days is within the difference uncertainty.

Figure 3.5.3: temporal differences between SPIRE and SMAP datasets (averaged spatially).

Figure 3.5.4 and Figure 3.5.5 show the maps of SPIRE and SMAP co-located measurements. These graphs have been built averaging together all co-located measurements in a certain region (1 deg latitude and 1 deg longitude) collected during the entire intercomparison period.

Figure 3.5.4: SPIRE soil moisture map.

As in CYGNSS case, both satellites observe an increase in the soil moisture from the inland to the coastal area. Even here, SPIRE map tends to overestimate soil moisture in the central region of the intercomparison area, extending from south-west to north-east, but the differences tend to be less pronounced as can be seen in Figure 3.5.6 and Figure 3.5.7.

Some spatial differences statistical parameters are reported in Table 4. Respect to CYGNSS the differences are centred on 0 value with a negligible mean and a similar standard deviation.

Figure 3.5.5: SMAP soil moisture map.

Table 4: SPIRE-SMAP spatial differences statistics

	mean	Standard deviation	min	max
Delta	0.029	0.070	-0.175	0.182

Figure 3.5.6: SPIRE vs SMAP difference map.

Figure 3.5.7: SPIRE vs SMAP relative difference map.

Figure 3.5.8 and Figure 3.5.9 show the uncertainty maps of the two satellites; to SMAP a fixed uncertainty value has been assigned, as described in the introduction. SPIRE uncertainty/standard deviation appear to be distributed in a different way with respect to CYGNSS; even here is higher in the central region, revealing a larger variability characterizing those pixels, with peaks in the north-east and south-east; the relative uncertainty of SPIRE reported in Figure 3.5.10 is generally below 30%, with an peak in the centre. SMAP relative uncertainty decrease moving from the desert to the coasts (Figure 3.5.11).

Figure 3.5.8: SPIRE uncertainty map (co-located SMAP).

Figure 3.5.9: SMAP uncertainty map (co-located SPIRE).

Figure 3.5.10: SPIRE relative uncertainty map.

Figure 3.5.11: SMAP relative uncertainty map.

Figure 3.5.12 reports the ratio between the map differences and the difference uncertainty: pixels with a large ratio are mixed with areas characterized by non-significant differences.

Figure 3.5.12: ratio between SPIRE vs SMAP difference and difference uncertainty.

3.5.2 Statistical analysis

Figure 3.5.13 shows the scatter plot between SMAP (x axis) and SPIRE (y axis) measurements. The fit results and bias analysis of the two datasets is reported in Table 5. Figure 3.5.14 reports the scatterplot obtained with 3 hours temporal threshold. Statistical results seem better but the number of points is too few to be considered statistically relevant.

Table 5: SPIRE vs SMAP statistics

SPIRE - SMAP	
Number of couples	780
Fit slope	0.79
Fit intercept	0.08
Correlation Coefficient	0.58
Bias Mean value	0.003
Bias Standard deviation	0.096
Mean uncertainty	0.054

Figure 3.5.13: SPIRE vs SMAP scatterplot.

Figure 3.5.14: SPIRE vs SMAP scatterplot (3 hours).

Figure 3.5.15 shows the measurements distribution of SPIRE and SMAP co-located couples in terms of relative occurrences of a certain measurement result (bin width equal to 0.04). Here we do not see the peak at 0.1 as in CYGNSS case: SMAP has its maximum at [0.24-0.28] bin, while SPIRE distribution presents a more pronounced right tail.

Figure 3.5.15: SPIRE and SMAP co-located measurements histogram.

Figure 3.5.16: SPIRE and SMAP co-located measurements histogram (3 hours).

Figure 3.5.16 shows the histogram obtained with 3 hours temporal threshold; both distribution presents oscillations, probably due to the low number of coincidences obtained using this threshold.

Figure 3.5.17: SPIRE vs SMAP qq-plots; (left) comparison of the two datasets with the gaussian theoretical distribution, (right) comparison of SPIRE and SMAP data distribution.

Figure 3.5.17 reports the result of the quantile-quantile plot. In the left panel each dataset (blue for SPIRE, purple for SMAP) has been compared with the gaussian distribution that best fits its measurements, represented by the blue and pink lines for SPIRE and SMAP datasets respectively. In the y-axis the values of measurements are represented, while the x-axis represents the values of a gaussian distribution expressed in terms of number of standard deviations. The two datasets have a similar shape of the left tail, showing a difference in the right tail.

The second panel is an inter-comparison of the distribution of the two datasets. The distribution of the quantiles of the two instruments shows again that the two datasets have a similar statistical distribution for the lower part of the measurement spectrum, until 0.25.

Figure 3.5.18: SPIRE-SMAP differences vs SMAP measurements.

Figure 3.5.19: number of couples per bin SPIRE-SMAP (bin width 0.04).

Figure 3.5.18 shows the differences between SPIRE and SMAP plotted against SMAP soil moisture (purple dots) and the mean and standard deviation of this difference. These last two quantities have been calculated dividing the measurements value in bins of 0.04. This graph shows a positive bias until [0.24-0.28] bin and a negative bias for higher soil moisture

value. The average bias is less pronounced with respect to CYGNSS. Figure 3.5.19 reports the number of couples per bin.

Figure 3.5.20: SPIRE-SMAP difference histogram

Figure 3.5.21: Histogram of ratio between difference and difference uncertainty. The coloured area is reported in the legend.

Figure 3.5.20 shows the histogram of the differences between SPIRE and SMAP and the results of a gaussian fit (dashed lines). The histogram bins width is again 0.04 and the gauss fit mean and standard deviation are reported in figure. Even this graph confirms the small mean bias between the datasets, while the standard deviation, greater than the

average uncertainty (see Table 5) suggests a consistent number of significant differences, as can be seen from Figure 3.5.21, that displays the histograms of the values of the ratio between SPIRE-SMAP differences and difference uncertainty. Histograms has been built using 1 width bins. The 45.4% of the couples present differences within their combined uncertainty (green area); the significant differences are more common in the right tail, yellow and red areas, with an occurrence of about 35.6%, while cyan and purple area, related to the negative significant, differences are 20% of the total.

Figure 3.5.22 shows the ratio between differences and combined uncertainties ($r = \Delta/\sigma$) as function of the SMAP measurement values (blue dots). The bins in this analysis are the same of those used for Figure 3.5.18. The green curve represents the average of the ratios calculated within a certain measurement bin (bins widths equal to 0.04), with the standard deviation shown by the green area. The frequency of ratios with absolute value larger than 1 (e.g., significant differences, larger than the combined uncertainty) per bin is displayed by the orange histogram in Figure 3.5.23. The ratios appear closer to the non-significant region with respect to CYGNSS, with a predominance of the significant differences in the high-soil moisture bins.

Figure 3.5.22: Study of the ratio between differences and uncertainties as function of SMAP measurements.

Figure 3.5.23: Significant differences occurrence per SMAP measurement bin (bin width 0.04).

3.6 SPIRE vs SMOS results

In this paragraph the results of SPIRE and SMOS soil moisture intercomparison will be discussed.

3.6.1 Spatial and temporal analysis

The following plots show a spatial and temporal analysis of SPIRE results, compared to SMOS measurements.

Figure 3.6.1: SPIRE-SMOS spatial distribution of the number of couples.

Figure 3.6.2: daily averages of SPIRE and CYGNSS measurements (spatially averaged on the entire intercomparison region).

Figure 3.6.1 shows the spatial distribution of the number of couples. The intercomparison region has been divided into sectors of 1 deg in latitude and longitude. SMOS measurements are in greater numbers with respect to the other two reference missions.

Figure 3.6.2 shows the daily averages of the SPIRE (blue) SMOS (green) results. Each dot represents the average value of the co-located measurements collected during a certain day on the entire intercomparison region. The shaded area represents the daily average of the uncertainty (averaged on the entire intercomparison region). The two timeseries appear to be correlated with SPIRE measuring higher soil moisture values than SMOS. Figure 3.6.3 shows the absolute and relative difference between the timeseries. The zero-difference line is marked in orange and the shaded area represent the difference uncertainty, calculated as squared sum of the shaded areas of the time-series plot.

Figure 3.6.3: temporal differences between SPIRE and SMOS datasets (averaged spatially).

Figure 3.6.4 and Figure 3.6.5 show the maps of SPIRE and SMOS co-located measurements. These graphs have been built averaging together all co-located measurements in a certain region (1 deg latitude and 1 deg longitude) collected during the entire intercomparison period. As in previous case, both satellites observe an increase in the soil moisture from the inland to the coastal area. SPIRE map tends to overestimate soil moisture in the central region even in this case, extending from south-west to north-east. The differences can be seen in Figure 3.6.6 and Figure 3.6.7. Some spatial differences statistical parameters are reported in Table 6.

Figure 3.6.4: SPIRE soil moisture map.

Figure 3.6.5: SMOS soil moisture map.

Table 6: SPIRE-SMOS spatial differences statistics

	mean	Standard deviation	Min	Max
Delta	0.037	0.068	-0.146	0.197

Figure 3.6.6: SPIRE vs SMOS difference map.

Figure 3.6.7: SPIRE vs SMOS relative difference map.

Figure 3.6.8 and Figure 3.6.9 show the uncertainty maps. SPIRE uncertainty/standard deviation appear to resemble the SMAP patterns; even here is higher in the central region, revealing a larger variability characterizing those pixels; the relative uncertainty of SPIRE reported in Figure 3.6.10 and it is generally below 30%. SMOS uncertainty is generally lower with respect to SPIRE (Figure 3.6.11).

Figure 3.6.8: SPIRE uncertainty map (co-located SMOS).

Figure 3.6.9: SMOS uncertainty map (co-located SPIRE).

Figure 3.6.10: SPIRE relative uncertainty map.

Figure 3.6.11: SMOS relative uncertainty map.

Figure 3.6.12 reports the ratio between the map differences and the difference uncertainty, revealing several areas characterized by significant differences; as in SMAP case we see a 'patchwork' of pixels with a large ratio and areas characterized by non-significant differences.

Figure 3.6.12: ratio between SPIRE vs SMOS difference and difference uncertainty.

3.6.2 Statistical analysis

Figure 3.6.13 shows the scatter plot between SMOS (x axis) and SPIRE (y axis) measurements. The fit results and bias analysis of the two datasets is reported in Table 3. Figure 3.6.14 reports also the scatterplot obtained using the three hours threshold to show the variation of the statistical parameters with less temporal distance between couples; for SMOS the diminution of the temporal threshold leads to a better comparison, improvements not visible in the other two cases.

Table 7: SPIRE vs SMOS statistics

	SPIRE – SMOS
Number of couples	3126
Fit slope	0.77
Fit intercept	0.09
Correlation Coefficient	0.64
Bias Mean value	0.037
Bias Standard deviation	0.095
Mean uncertainty	0.040

Figure 3.6.13: SPIRE vs SMOS scatterplot.

Figure 3.6.14: SPIRE and SMOS 3 hours co-located measurements histogram.

Figure 3.6.15: SPIRE and SMOS co-located measurements histogram.

Figure 3.6.16: SPIRE and SMOS 3 hours co-located measurements histogram.

Figure 3.6.15 shows the measurements distribution of SPIRE and SMOS co-located couples in terms of relative occurrences of a certain measurement result (bin width equal to 0.04). SMOS is characterized by a double peak shape; as in the previous intercomparison, SPIRE has a larger occurrence in the right tail, but this time the discrepancy starts from 0.32. Figure 3.6.16 again present the results obtained for 3 hours temporal threshold in order to show the discrepancy reduction due to the reduction of the temporal distance, even if the larger occurrence of SPIRE measurements in the right tail

remains present. Even in this intercomparison the next plots will refer to the 8 hours threshold study.

Figure 3.6.17: SPIRE vs SMOS qq-plots; (left) comparison of the two datasets with the gaussian theoretical distribution, (right) comparison of SPIRE and CYGNSS data distribution.

Figure 3.6.17 reports the result of the quantile-quantile plot. The left panel compares each dataset (blue for SPIRE, green for SMOS) with the gaussian distribution that best fits its measurements, represented by the blue and green lines for SPIRE and SMOS datasets respectively. In the y-axis the values of measurements are represented, while the x-axis represents the values of a gaussian distribution expressed in terms of number of standard deviations. The two datasets have a similar distribution of the low values of soil moisture, diverging in the upper part of the measurement spectrum. The second panel is an inter-comparison of the distribution of the two datasets. The distribution of the quantiles of the two instruments shows again that the two datasets have a similar statistical distribution for the lower part of the measurement spectrum, until 0.22, diverging for higher values.

Figure 3.6.18: SPIRE-SMOS differences vs SMOS measurements.

Figure 3.6.19: number of couples per bin (bin width 0.04).

Figure 3.6.18 shows the differences between SPIRE and SMOS plotted against SMOS soil moisture (light green dots) and the mean and standard deviation of this difference (green dots and areas). These last two quantities have been calculated dividing the measurements value in bins of 0.04 of. This graph shows a positive bias with a maximum in the [0.16-0.20] bin, decreasing for higher soil moisture results and becoming negative for bins above 0.34. The oscillations in the right part of the plot could be statistical fluctuations (see Figure 3.6.19).

Figure 3.6.20: SPIRE-SMOS difference histogram

Figure 3.6.21: Histogram of ratio between difference and difference uncertainty. The coloured area is reported in the legend.

Figure 3.6.20 shows the histogram of the differences between SPIRE and SMOS and the results of a gaussian fit (dashed lines). The histogram bins width is again 0.04 and the gauss fit mean and standard deviation are reported in figure. SPIRE-SMOS differences seems to follow more a gaussian distribution with respect to the previous intercomparison.

Figure 3.6.21 displays the histograms of the values of the ratio between SPIRE-CYGNSS differences and difference uncertainty. Histograms has been built using 1 width bins. The 29.1% of the couples present differences within their combined uncertainty (green area), while the larger part present significant positive differences (red and yellow areas, 47.9%); cyan and purple areas referring to significant negative differences represent just less than 19% of the total. The large occurrence of significant differences here could be related to the small uncertainty of SMOS Δ measurements.

Figure 3.6.22 shows the ratio between differences and combined uncertainties ($r = \Delta/\sigma$) as function of the SMOS measurement values (blue dots). The bins in this analysis are the same of those used for Figure 3.6.18. The green curve represents the average of the ratios calculated within a certain measurement bin (bins widths equal to 0.04), with the standard deviation shown by the green area. The frequency of ratios with absolute value larger than 1 (e.g., significant differences, larger than the combined uncertainty) per bin is displayed by the green histogram in Figure 3.6.23. The higher occurrences of significant differences with respect to the previous intercomparisons, are caused by the dispersion of measurements, and the bias affecting the two datasets and the lower SMAP uncertainty.

Figure 3.6.22: study of the ratio between differences and uncertainties as function of SMOS measurements.

Figure 3.6.23: Significant differences occurrence per SMOS measurement bin (bin width 0.04).

3.7 Results Compliance

According to the criteria published in RD-2 we propose for the intercomparison exercise, a Validation Method between Good and Excellent. The Good grade is assigned, citing RD-2, for methodology that “covers a range of satellite measurements that represents typical use cases, using representative reference measurements. Uncertainty information not available for reference data”, while Excellent grade is assigned for methodology that “assesses satellite measurements and reference data with respect to their characterised uncertainties. Reference measurements are assessed to be well representative of the satellite measurements.” In this work we presented an assessment that largely employs the uncertainties given in references datasets as requested by the excellent grade. The second requirement for the excellent grade is the assessment of a dataset well representative of the satellite measurements. The SPIRE datasets analysed is limited to about one month of data over south-east Australia. The excellent grade should be fully achieved with a larger dataset, covering more latitudes, and extending into the four seasons.

Figure 3.6.2.1: mean values of differences as function of the reference measurements for 8 hours threshold.

Figure 3.6.2.1 reports the mean differences as function of the reference measurements for all comparison references examined in the study; the standard deviations are indicated by vertical bars; the comparison results agreed, with CYGNSS having a more positive bias with respect to the others. Correlation coefficient found for the 8 hours temporal threshold are about 0.6 for all the three missions. The difference between the measurements is particularly evident for higher values of soil moisture as suggested by the qq-plots and measurement distributions graphs; this is more pronounced for CYGNSS, see Figure 3.6.2.2, while SMOS and SMAP present similar qq-plots.

Figure 3.6.2.2: SPIRE vs references qq-plots for 8 hours threshold.

Figure 3.6.2.3: SPIRE vs references qq-plots for 3 hours threshold.

The temporal threshold chosen for the intercomparison could have an important impact on the intercomparison results: SMAP and SMOS measurements are collected at dawn and dusk, while SPIRE datasets is mainly composed of morning measurements. This discrepancy could lead to different measurement conditions; however, the test done with different temporal threshold reported in Table 1, reveals that decreasing this value we obtained better results for SMOS intercomparison. The results obtained for SMAP and

CYGNSS are more controversial: we found an improvement of the correlation coefficient for the three hours threshold case for SMAP and one hour for CYGNSS, however the small number of points of this test does not allow to consider it as statistical significative. A further investigation on the region at the centre of the intercomparison area, characterized by larger differences could be useful to better understand their nature.

In order to provide a comparison with the eight hours threshold case study, Figure 3.6.2.3 and Figure 3.6.2.4 report the mean bias and qq-plots obtained using three hours threshold. The bias structure is similar, with more oscillations due to the presence of less couples, while SMAP and SMOS qq-plots tend to slightly move away from the ideal agreement with respect to previous case.

Figure 3.6.2.4: SPIRE vs references qq-plots for 3 hours threshold.

According to the criteria published in RD-2 we propose a Validation Results grade of Basic for both CYGNSS and SMAP and a grade Good for SMOS. In both the first two intercomparisons we found some agreement between measurements, however the correlation coefficient of about 0.6, the bias and the different statistical distribution of the two datasets does not allow to reach higher grades. In particular we note that, although CYGNSS is nominally the calibration mission for the analysed measurements, it does not present a better agreement with respect to the other two missions.

SMOS, in our opinion reaches the Good grade thanks to the improvement in the results obtained decreasing the temporal threshold (correlation coefficient increment to 0.77 and more, see Table 1), suggesting that part of the examined discrepancy can be ascribed at the different measurement conditions. Unfortunately, the decrease in the temporal threshold does not lead to improvement in the other two missions that can be considered statistically significative due to the small number of couples found.

The horizontal resolutions of all the examined products are of the order of several km², order of magnitude greater than the geometrical accuracy requested for correct satellites geo-localization; for this reason, we considered the Geometrical Validation outside of the scope of this study, and the spatial parameters and accuracies provided by the data suitable for the type of measurement provided by the mission.

APPENDIX A Mission Test Dataset

Reference	Product Identifier (L1 and L2)
SMAP	<p>SMAP L2 Radiometer Half-Orbit 36 km EASE-Grid Soil Moisture, Version 6, DATA SET ID: SPL2SMP, DOI: 10.5067/R50VUC07OM4W</p> <p>O'Neill, P. E., S. Chan, E. G. Njoku, T. Jackson, R. Bindlish, and J. Chaubell. (2019). SMAP L2 Radiometer Half-Orbit 36 km EASE-Grid Soil Moisture, Version 6 [Data Set]. Boulder, Colorado USA. NASA National Snow and Ice Data Center Distributed Active Archive Center. https://doi.org/10.5067/R50VUC07OM4W. Date Accessed 08-03-2023.</p>
CYGNSS	<p>CYGNSS. 2020. UCAR-CU CYGNSS Level 3 Soil Moisture Version 1.0. Ver. 1.0, Dataset Accessed at 2023-07-15 at https://doi.org/10.5067/CYGNU-L3SM1</p> <p>Chew, C.C., E. E. Small, 2020. Description of the UCAR/CU Soil Moisture Product, Remote Sens, 12, 10. https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12101558</p>
SMOS	<p>SMOS L1 and L2 Science data, accessed on 31st July 2023, available at https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/catalog/smos-science-products</p>

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